

January 2022 NICEST2 newsletter

20th January 2022

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FAIR for Climate Science in the Nordics

Activity lead by *Hamish Struthers (SNIC, Sweden)*

The NeIC-NICEST2 staff attended the Metadata for Machines workshop (M4M) organized by EOSC-Nordic for the Climate Community and it was a great success!

What did we learn?

An excellent introduction to the technicalities and tools for generating and managing controlled vocabularies (ontologies), and how to make controlled vocabularies publicly available via existing portals. The workshop included nice hands-on exercises utilizing a data set provided by one of the participants. A short review of the workshop, including links to the workshop material was posted in the [December EOSC-Nordic newsletter](#).

What's our follow up plan?

It is important to follow up on the initial workshop outcomes. A mailing list is being set up along with [a shared document](#). A follow up meeting is also planned for later in January. Anyone is welcome to participate (email struthers-at-nsc.liu.se). We also have set up an open chat discussion channel with [zulip](#) and you can join us on <https://fairdm.zulipchat.com/>: you can listen in, follow certain threads, participate, and influence.

Diagnostics for Earth System Modelling: Help us to help you!

Activity lead by *Tommi Bergman (FMI, Finland)*

In the NeIC-NICEST2 project we have some funding for adapting/transforming existing diagnostics into ESMValTool diagnostics for the benefit of Nordic researchers. We are now asking for suggestions regarding which diagnostics would be important in the Nordics. These can be small code snippets or references to published papers.

We are asking for you to fill out a [very short questionnaire](#) (less than 2 minutes to fill it before February 4th, 2022) to gather information on new diagnostics (ad-hoc tools developed in any programming languages, ESMValTool recipes, etc.) and information on the usage of ESMValTool.

Link to the questionnaire: <https://forms.gle/AxS7apMXKw6Po5iu5>

As we also would like to get some usage statistics please do fill out the questionnaire even if you are not able to share diagnostics.

Lumi and NICEST2: a joint interest for joint resources

Activity lead by Jean Iaquina (UiO, Norway)

Our first experience with EuroHPC has been a success with the use of containers which worked out-of-the box from day one of the Lumi pilot phase. However, the current allocation "process" forced us to work "in silos" e.g. only Norwegian NeIC-NICEST2 staff were able to access Lumi computing resources during the pilot phase. Since we are working on the definition of "standardised" Earth System Modelling workflows through the use of containers and workflow management systems, we believe that having joint access to Lumi would benefit the NeIC-NICEST2 staff, and more generally the Nordic climate community.

Are you using GPUs and working in the field of Climate science?

Then we would like to hear from you!

Our next seminar series will be dedicated to GPUs and Climate science and we are gathering a list of potential presenters (email jeani-at-uio-no). The idea behind these seminars is to demystify GPUs and collect practical examples highlighting the benefits of GPUs beyond "toy use cases", typically for pre- and post-processing, vizualization, storage, etc. (and not only for the ESM simulations).

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